

VIRTIGATION – Emerging viral diseases in tomatoes and cucurbits: Implementation of mitigation strategies for durable disease management

Deliverable Nr. 4.5
 Report on the risks of multiple infections for resistance and strategies of virus control

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations used :

DAS	Days after sowing
DPI	Days post inoculation
DSMZ	Deutsche Sammlung von Mikroorganismen und Zellkulturen
RT-qPCR	Real-time quantitative reverse transcription PCR

Virus acronyms

CABYV	Cucurbit aphid-borne yellows virus, polerovirus
CCYV	Cucurbit chlorotic yellows virus, crinivirus
CMV	Cucumber mosaic virus, cucumovirus
CVYV	Cucumber vein yellowing virus, ipomovirus
CYSVDV	Cucurbit yellow stunting disease virus, crinivirus
MWMV	Moroccan watermelon mosaic virus, potyvirus
PepMV	Pepino mosaic virus, potexvirus
ToBRFV	Tomato brown rugose fruit virus, tobamovirus
ToLCNDV	Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus, begomovirus
WMV	Watermelon mosaic virus, potyvirus
ZYMV	Zucchini yellow mosaic virus, potyvirus

1 PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The prevalence of viral infections in crops is projected to increase as climate change drives shifts in virus and vector distribution, creating conditions that favor mixed infections. These complex interactions pose significant challenges for crop health and productivity, as they can undermine existing control strategies and genetic resistance. The present report addresses these emerging risks by examining how new virus combinations affect particularly tomato and cucurbit crops, with a focus on resistance durability and commonly used management practices.

Two major and emergent viral pathogens were investigated, the begomovirus Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (ToLCNDV), a bipartite virus with a genome composed of two circular ssDNA molecules, and transmitted efficiently by whiteflies, primarily impacting cucurbits in Europe; and the tobamovirus Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV), a highly stable virus that easily spreads by mechanical means and has become a major constraint in tomato production across Europe, North America, and the Middle East despite the attempts to implement strict hygiene measures.

Mixed infections involving these viruses and unrelated ones are increasingly common, raising concerns about synergistic or antagonistic interactions and their combined impact on crop performance. The findings presented in this report, developed under the VIRTIGATION project, provide updated insights into critical factors for managing pathogenic viruses under mixed infection conditions. These include the durability of genetic resistance, the influence of non-target viruses on integrated control strategies, and the implications for sustainable crop protection.

2 INTRODUCTION

Emergence of virus diseases and modifications of crops and vector geographical limits due to climate change was predicted to result in more prevalence of viral mixed infections. The problem addressed in the tasks included in this report was to find out how the risks associated to new combinations of viruses in tomato and cucurbit crops could be better estimated. For this, we have analyzed the outcomes of co-infections (simultaneous inoculation) and of super-infections (one virus infecting a plant that was already infected by other virus).

In the case of ToLCNDV, to approach natural situations occurring in fields, in certain combinations the inoculation procedures were performed through releasing viruliferous vectors in controlled conditions like growth chambers, or the plants were directly tested in fields under semi commercial conditions to receive natural infections from circulating vectors (these activities are fully detailed in a different report, Deliverable 5.6).

For ToBRFV, inoculations were performed mechanically, and the severity of symptoms observed, with a description of their dynamics along time in mixed infections to characterize synergistic, antagonistic or neutral interactions, giving particular attention to the interactions with virus strains of unrelated viruses commonly detected in tomato.

3 CHAPTER 1: ROLE OF MIXED INFECTIONS INVOLVING ToLCNDV IN RESISTANCE AND TRANSMISSION

This chapter reports the experiments performed by CRAG researchers with the leading role of postdoc Mireia Uranga Ruiz de Eguino and the PhD candidate Clara Ontañón in growth chamber conditions at CRAG, taking advantage of the available BSL2 facilities, as required by safety procedures at CRAG, to work with a ToLCNDV isolate (kindly provided by collaborators from CSIC partner, Jesús Navas and Elvira Fiallo Olivé in the form of infectious cloned material).

The materials tested included susceptible cultivars such as Védraçais melon, kindly provided by partner Cecile Desbiez from INRAE, and tested in our BSL2 facilities in collaboration during a brief stay of student Atiwich Patthamapornosirikul at CRAG. Other melon accessions were provided by our collaborator Carmelo López del Rincón (COMAV, UPV, Valencia, Spain), and they were propagated by partner HuertaValle Hibri2 in order to have enough seeds for subsequent experiments (described in more detail in the report corresponding to Deliverable 5.6).

The experiments at CRAG were evaluated through regular visual assessment and symptoms scoring (scale 0-4, being 0 no symptoms and 4 severe symptoms), alongside with molecular diagnostic techniques for virus detection, usually RT-PCR for RNA-viruses, and tissue-print hybridization with a virus-specific DIG-labelled probe for routinary detection of ToLCNDV. Also Real Time PCR analysis was implemented during the collaborative work with INRAE for quantification purposes.

The final analysis of selected laboratory-infected controls at CRAG were performed along with some field samples using RNAseq after in-house RNA extraction and ribodepleted library preparations, deep sequencing and analysis with the Genome Detective tool developed by VIRTIGATION partner EmWeb (see Deliverable D5.6).

3.1 Mixed infections in controlled conditions

The combination of begomovirus and other viruses has been addressed previously in our laboratory in tomato, while in melon we considered mixed infections of different viruses, as the begomovirus ToLCNDV was not previously analyzed because it required BSL2 conditions in the region where CRAG is located (Cataluña, Spain).

Therefore, to complete later studies, a first comparison was performed in BSL2 conditions between susceptible melon plants (local "Piel de Sapo" cultivar) and seeds claimed by local seed providers that could be considered tolerant to several viruses. In assays involving individual virus inoculation with ToLCNDV, the scoring of the susceptible line was consistently in the range 3-4, with only a few asymptomatic plants, most likely escapes due to failure of whitefly inoculation. On the other hand, the materials expected to be tolerant only exhibited mild (53% of plants, score 1) or no symptoms (47%, score 0).

To explore to what extent the mixed infection of other viruses could be detrimental for these tolerances, we selected two candidate viruses: the cucumovirus CMV as an ubiquitous virus, in this case transmitted by aphids, and expected to be present in many co-infections; and also the ipomovirus CVYV, which was chosen considering its proximity to potyviruses, often involved in synergisms. Since ipomoviruses are efficiently transmitted by whiteflies, sharing the same vector for ToLCNDV, we expected to find them together under natural conditions if vectors are essential for virus dispersal.

The accession selected were PI 414723 due to its expected tolerance against ToLCNDV, and accession PI 313970 as a common source of resistances/tolerances to different viruses.

3.1.1 Mix infection of ToLCNDV plus the cucumovirus CMV

Two complete experiments were performed, using Védrançais melon as susceptible control, and groups of individual plants in each treatment for either single or mixed inoculations. The inoculation method for CMV was mechanical (a single application). For ToLCNDV, both mechanical inoculation (with two consecutive applications of the inocula with a 7 day gap between the first and second inoculation) and insect-mediated inoculation with viruliferous whiteflies were tested; in both cases, infected susceptible zucchini plants with severe symptoms and high virus titers were used as ToLCNDV source inocula.

Concerning the single inoculations, CMV was successfully inoculated to both PI 414723 and PI313970 plants. Regarding ToLCNDV alone, Védrançais was found to be susceptible as expected (around 80% of plants infected), while PI414723 behaved as tolerant (symptoms milder than in Védrançais, again around 80% of plants infected), and no apparent infections were detected in the case of PI313970. However, in co-infected plants with the two viruses, the scoring of symptoms in 40% of the PI414723 suggested possible effects at late stages (28 dpi), although still no positive detection of ToLCNDV for PI313970, despite observing severe leaf curling in young newly emerging leaves in a few plants, which could indicate an unusual CMV infection symptom (but detected in all plants), or a putative synergism that requires further confirmation.

The observed scores for symptoms on plants exposed to mixed infections are summarized in the table below:

Mix Infections	0	1	2	3	4
Védrançais	80%	0%	0%	10%	10%
PI313970	46%	0%	0%	46%	8%
PI414723	46%	0%	0%	46%	8%

3.1.2 Mix infection of ToLCNDV plus the ipomovirus CVYV

Preliminary tests with a limited number of plants showed that Védrançais was fully susceptible to both viruses individually, with an unexpected symptom of unopened flower buds in single inoculation with CVYV. Mixed infections showed severe symptoms at late stages (>30 dpis), in a similar trend to the single ToLCNDV infections, while other characteristic symptoms of CVYV were absent, suggesting a possible antagonistic effect.

Subsequent experiments were performed with the cultivar "Piel de sapo" (corresponding to C61 in the materials provided by Carmelo López, thus named as PS-C61) as susceptible material, in order to compare with a commercial seed claimed resistant to ToLCNDV (PS-Co). We observed after molecular detection a high rate of mixed infections in both cases: all plants were infected by ToLCNDV and 50% corresponded to mixed infections in the case of PS-C61, while for PS-Co 70% corresponded to mixed infections. Semiquantitative RT-PCR suggested no differences in viral load for CVYV when ToLCNDV was present, revealing no antagonistic response at the molecular level despite the alterations of symptoms, with a more stunted phenotype observed in some plants of PS-Co compared to PS-C61.

It is relevant to indicate that for PS-Co a proportion (about 20%) of plants showed compromised tolerance when CVYV was present

The scores corresponding to mixed infections are summarized in the table below:

Mix Infections	0	1	2	3	4
PS-Co	80%	0%	10%	10%	0%
PS-C61	50%	0%	0%	50%	0%

3.2 Natural mixed infections in field conditions

The field testing were performed in the Málaga region with seeds corresponding to the following melon materials: PS-C61, PS-Co, P31, PI 313970, PI 414723, P201, and located in a commercial greenhouse (coordinates: 36°48'32.1"N 4°08'15.8"W) and open field (coordinates: 36°45'45.2"N 4°00'23.6"W). The support of a local service provider, Juan Antonio Rodríguez from Agrotropiche S.L. was instrumental for the experiments.

Analysis of the samples (more details in the report corresponding to the Deliverable D5.6) revealed the presence of ToLCNDV as a single infection in one plant of the genotype P201, in a mixed infection with CABYV in PS (a double infection), and in PS-Co and in PI 414723 the presence of quadruple infections including MWMV, CABYV, and CCYV. Interestingly, some of the detected viruses in samples taken from contiguous plants in the same field were aphid transmitted (MWMV and CABYV, and CMV, which are not associated to ToLCNDV), while CCYV is a whitefly-transmitted crinivirus, indicating that at least the two vectors are involved in the dissemination of viruses in the region. This is coincidental with the observations reported in the literature, and further confirmed the data included in the Deliverable 5.6.

3.3 Agronomic performance and mixed infections in zucchini

The results described in this sections derive from the samples and data generated by partner APREL and analyzed by INRAE when comparing eleven selected zucchini cultivars in two experiments conducted in 2024 and 2025, to evaluate their agronomic performance for Deliverable 5.6. The selected cultivars were chosen as representative of the new cultivars expected to be either resistant to ToLCNDV, or at least exhibit tolerance to this pathogen, allowing a commercially profitable cultivation by producers.

Most cultivars showed intermediate resistance to WMV, ZYMV, and ToLCNDV, except cultivar J, which only exhibited theoretical tolerance to ToLCNDV. Under moderate viral pressure in 2024, cultivars E and F achieved significantly higher yields than the control, while others performed less well in terms of yield. Viral analysis revealed WMV and CABYV as the most prevalent infections, detected in over 60% of plants. ToLCNDV was present in 50% of control plants, with 32% showing symptoms, whereas resistant cultivars displayed minor symptoms (10–40%) without significant impact on growth or fruit production. Notably, ToLCNDV was absent in cultivars E, B, and C and detected only in a few plants of cultivars F and L, suggesting a promising opportunities for farmers to adopt resistant material.

However, the second trial in 2025 under high viral pressure produced markedly different results. Severe symptoms appeared early on leaves and fruits, and none of the cultivars maintained good agronomic performance. ToLCNDV infection rates ranged from 50% to 90% across all cultivars, including the previously considered to exhibit certain tolerance. The susceptible control ceased growth after the first harvest week, while resistant cultivars stopped by the second week. Co-infections with WMV and CABYV were frequent, highlighting the role of both whiteflies and aphids in virus dispersal and the complexity of mixed infections.

In conclusion, while some cultivars like E and F can tolerate virus pressure under moderate conditions, this tolerance collapses when overall viral pressure becomes too high. Resistant cultivars reduce symptom severity but do not prevent virus presence, confirming that they remain hosts. These findings underscore the need for integrated management strategies that consider mixed infections and vector dynamics to sustain crop productivity.